

ELIMINATION OF THE THREAT OF EXTREMISM AND SECURITY IN UZBEKISTAN

Kurbanov Djamshid Djurayevich

Head of the Department of UNI Academic Lyceum,

Independent Researcher of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation: In the conditions of globalization, ensuring security and stability in Central Asia is gaining importance. This article analyzes the threats of religious extremism, which seeks to threaten security and stability on a global scale, and the issues of combating it.

Keywords: religious extremism, development, information, movement, separatism, immunity

Nowadays, there have been changes in the tactical approaches of activities related to the promotion of the ideas of terrorism and religious extremism, that is, social networks are facilitating the promotion and recruitment of religious-extremist structures (terrorist organizations). Through these ideas, false ideas about Islam and Muslims are being created. This indicates that extremists use various forms of propaganda to confuse the minds of ordinary people.

One of the important tasks in this direction is the development of measures aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the fight against emerging risks and threats.

Based on the above, it is worth noting the following:

firstly, different political forces are using the religion of Islam for their own interests;

secondly, the exposure of citizens to extremist ideas creates threats to the security of the state and society;

thirdly, there is a need to improve measures against the spread of religious-extremist ideas.

Our main tasks in the prevention of religious extremism:

- organizing conversations about the terrible manifestations and negative consequences of religious extremism in various organizations, educational institutions and labor groups located in the region;
- collecting information and information about religious extremist movements and organizations;
- reporting to the law enforcement body about religious extremist movements, organizations and persons related to this movement.

Extremism has become the most dangerous and unpredictable phenomenon in modern times. Acts of extremism lead to the premature death of innocent people, the destruction of material and spiritual resources that serve the well-being of society, and the destruction of people's peaceful daily life. Especially in today's dangerous and complicated times, tense situations and mutual conflicts around the world are causing various conflicts between nations and religions, and are also derailing the existing order established in the world.

At the same time, it is observed that destructive groups that commit extremist and terrorist acts are not limited to one country or region, but are organized in different regions of the world. This puts the issue of cooperation of the countries of the world in the fight against extremism and terrorism and increasing the effectiveness of international and regional organizations on the agenda. One of the most important issues in this regard is that all members of the international community fully comply with the agreements on the fight against extremism and fulfill their obligations.

Uzbekistan's participation in the fight against extremism and terrorism is clearly manifested in its activities in regional organizations. In particular, it actively participates in the implementation of agreements aimed at combating extremism and terrorism adopted within the framework of a number of regional organizations such as the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe, the Commonwealth of Independent States, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, the Eurasian Economic

Cooperation Organization, and the Organization of Islamic Cooperation. In particular, the placement of the Anti-Terror Center within the framework of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization in Tashkent is also a recognition of our republic's activity in the fight against extremism and terrorism. After all, the participation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in agreements on the fight against extremism and terrorism is a logical continuation of its domestic and foreign policy.

The development of cooperation in the fight against “three evil forces”, namely “terrorism”, “separatism” and “extremism” occupies a special place in the activities of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization. As part of the organization's fight against extremism and terrorism, the military structures of our republic regularly participate in military training exercises against terrorist forces.

Priority VI of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, which consists of seven priority directions developed in our country based on the principle of “From the strategy of actions to the strategy of development”, is devoted to the issue of “Approaching universal problems based on national interests” processed:

- implementation of an effective state policy to fight against extremism and terrorism, which allows to ensure the rights and freedoms of citizens;
- improvement of preventive mechanisms aimed at preventing the factors that cause extremism and terrorism, improving the social and spiritual environment, preventing the influence of foreign ideas and eliminating their problems through systematic work with those who are influenced by them;
- formation of strong and stable immunity of the population, especially the young generation, against the ideology of terrorism and extremism;
- improvement of the international legal basis of combating extremism and terrorism and expansion of the contractual and legal basis of cooperation with foreign countries, regional and international organizations in the field of combating extremism and terrorism;

- exchange of information and experience with foreign countries and international organizations in the fight against extremism, terrorism and their financing;
- active participation in international and regional organizations whose activities are aimed at combating extremism and terrorism;
- Coordinating joint efforts to implement the UN Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy in Central Asia within the framework of the joint action plan;
- Expanding the role of Uzbekistan in the implementation of international initiatives that help to develop information exchange and cooperation within the framework of joint efforts to fight extremism and terrorism in Central Asia;
- to accelerate initiatives to attract the attention of the world community and regional organizations to ensure peace and harmony in Afghanistan and to involve this country in regional cooperation processes, including the fight against extremism and terrorism.

REFERENCES:

5. Safarova N. O. Classification of Modern Terrorism //International Journal of Humanities and Social Science. – 2011. – T. 1. – №. 13. – С. 111-114.
6. Safarova N. O. Terrorism as a political phenomenon //International Journal of Academic Research. – 2010. – T. 2. – №. 2.
7. Safarova N. O. Terror. Violence. Destructive //Вопросы гуманитарных наук. – 2010. – №. 1. – С. 251-253.
8. Safarova N. Terrorism (tarikhi-falsafiyahlil). – 2009.
9. Rakhmanov R., Olimovna N. S. Sources of violence seen in biosocial nature of man //Asian journal of social sciences & humanities. – 2012. – T. 1. – №. 2. – С. 142.
10. Olimovna N. S. Mass And Individual Terror //International Journal of Business and Social Science. – 2011. – T. 2. – №. 19.

11. Sobirovich T. B. National and universal principles of democracy //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 1. – C. 334-338.
12. Sobirovich T. B. The implementation of human indicator reforms in Uzbekistan //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2021. – T. 10. – №. 9. – C. 197-202.
13. Sobirovich T. B. National Principles of Democracy in Uzbekistan //Mediterranean Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences (MJBAS). – 2021. – T. 5. – №. 3. – C. 131-135.
14. Sobirovich T. B. Philosophical Dialectics of National and Universal Cultural Development //Irish Interdisciplinary Journal of Science & Research (IIJSR). – 2021.
15. Turdiyev B. S. The role of national harmony in the strategy of spiritual renewal //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – T. 1. – №. 6. – C. 229-233.
16. Sobirovich T. B. Strategy of Renewal of National Spirituality of Uzbekistan //International Journal on Integrated Education. – 2020. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 122-126.
17. Sobirovich T. B. Strategy of spiritual renewal in Uzbekistan //International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – T. 24. – №. 06.
18. Sobirovich T. B. The criterion of human indicators in development and renewals in Uzbekistan //EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR). – 2020. – T. 6. – №. 8. – C. 509-511.
19. Sobirovich T. B. O‘zbekiston demokratik jamiyat taraqqiyoti rivojida ma’naviy yangilanishlar strategiyasining roli //Imom Buxoriy saboqlari. – 2020. – №. 2. – C. 118-121.

20. Turdiyev B. The development of democratic society and spiritual renewal in the views of eastern and western thinkers //Общество и инновации. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1/s. – С. 710-717.

21. Sobirovich T. B. The Strategy of Cultural Development in Central Asia During Amir Temur and the Temurids Dynasty //Int. J. Sci. Res. in Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2021. – Т. 2021.

22. Sobirovich T. B. O ‘zbekistonning ma’naviy yangilanish strategiyasi //Buxoro:“Sadriddin Salim Buxoriy” Durdona nashriyoti. – 2020. – С. 48.

23. Sobirovich T. B. Evolution of ideas and views on the development of democratic society and spiritual renewals //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – №. 10. – С. 243-250.

24. Sobirovich T. B., Sharipovna A. F. NEW UZBEKISTAN–NEW STRATEGY OF ADMINISTRATIVE REFORMS //researchgate. net.

25. Turdiyev Bexruz Sobirovich. Ma’naviy yangilanish: yangi qaror va hayotbaxsh islohotlar strategiyasi. //Buxoro davlat universiteti Ilmiy axboroti. Buxoro: 2018. - № 2 (70). –P.208-213.

26. Turdiyev B. THE CONTRIBUTION OF BOBUR AND BOBURI DYNASTY TO THE RENEWAL OF WORLD CIVILIZATION //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 5. – №. 5.

27. Turdiyev B. Behbudi’s views on the spiritual renewal of society //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 5. – №. 5.